

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 7/4/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N2-3/W1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top:	Bottom:
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:		Width: **	Length:	Depth: 20 cm

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
①	CLAY - (like sand ?)	Tan	Compressed Packed	Slightly Rubbly	T	Lm ✓ <i>Some Small</i>	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
★ ②	Gypsum - Limes- tone (Crushed?)	white	Compact	Rub Rubbly	T	Lm ✓ <i>Frag Thru out</i>	Gp
						Gr	Char ✓ <i>Some FLECKS</i>
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ 2 No./ 26	B&W: Roll/ 2 No./ 18
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20	Feature Plan:	Sections: 1:10 Section
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: * Fd7 w End Beginning of general anomalous area
↳ SW corner

** D7 Actually whole w end Anomalous NE Area

* Yellowish Tan - on surface at W side of depression ① - slopes to ②
Probably Represents incomplete removal of deposit during N5 78 excavation - R4

BEDROCK PINK to RUST RED TRACES